

Impact of Neutron Library and Thermal Conductivity on PWR Axial Stability

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate the impact of different neutron data evaluations on the axial stability of the Olkiluoto 3 reactor. Specifically, we compare the measured and predicted axial offset during an intentionally started transient where the axial power distribution was allowed to oscillate freely for about 70 hours. Calculated results are derived using Studsvik's state-of-the-art core monitoring system CMS5.

The neutron data evaluations studied are ENDF-BVII.I (with and without the advanced resonance upscatter model in CASMO5), ENDF-BVIII.0, ENDF-BVIII.I, JEF-2.2, JEFF3.2, JENDL4 and JENDL5. For JENDL5, we also study evaluations where data is replaced by the corresponding ENDF-BVII.I-data for ¹H, ^{155/157}Gd, ²³⁵U, and ²³⁸U. An additional model based on JENDL5 is derived with the resonance overlap model activated for all nuclides. It is shown that the model based on ENDF-BVII.I with resonance upscatter activated gives the best results.

For the model based on ENDF-BVII.I we also perform a sensitivity study of varying heat conduction parameters for the fuel and the gap between cladding and pellet. It is shown that the parameters that gives the best agreement between measured and calculated damping ratio, gives worse agreement between the measured and calculated oscillation period, and vice versa. Consequently, the default parameter values in CMS5 are optimal in the sense that adjusting them in any direction will deteriorate either the damping ratio agreement or the oscillation period agreement.

Keywords: axial stability, PWR, EPR

1. INTRODUCTION

The Olkiluoto Nuclear Power Plant is located on the Olkiluoto island, on the west coast of Finland, and is owned and operated by Teollisuuden Voima Oyj, TVO. It consists of two BWRs of 890 MW each (Olkiluoto 1 and 2) and an EPR of 1600 MW (Olkiluoto 3). This analysis was performed on Olkiluoto 3, cycle 1.

Cycle 1 was designed to operate for about 18 months. The enrichment of the fuel ranges from 1.9 w/o to 3.3 w/o and Gadolinium is used as burnable poison. The Gadolinium loading is 12 rods with 9.0 w/o Gadolinium. The loading pattern is shown below.

Figure 1. Loading pattern of Olkiluoto 3, cycle 1

The core models are based on CASMO5 and SIMULATE5 and the following neutron data evaluations: ENDF-BVII.I (with and without the advanced resonance upscatter model in CASMO5 [1]), ENDF-BVIII.0, ENDF-BVIII.I, JEF-2.2, JEFF3.2, JENDL4 and JENDL5. For JENDL5, we also study evaluations where data is replaced by the corresponding ENDF-BVII.I-data for ^1H , $^{155/157}\text{Gd}$, ^{235}U , and ^{238}U . An additional model based on JENDL5 is derived with the resonance overlap model activated for all nuclides.

2. AXIAL XENON OSCILLATIONS

If the neutron flux in a thermal reactor is high enough that xenon burnup due to thermal absorption can exceed the delayed production of xenon due to decay of iodine, changes in xenon concentration may act as positive reactivity feedback following an initial perturbation. If the reactor is also large compared to the thermal neutron migration length, spatial xenon oscillations may occur. It is clear that almost every thermal power reactor fulfils these criteria. Although spatial xenon oscillations can occur both in the radial and the axial direction, this paper deals only with axial xenon oscillations in pressurized water reactors (PWRs).

At beginning of cycle (BOC), the axial power distribution will have the shape of a cosine curve, due to axial leakage. As the core depletes, the central parts of the core will deplete at a faster rate than the endzones and the power distribution flattens and may even become double-humped towards the end of the cycle. Also, the concentration of ^{239}Pu increases in the fuel due to breeding, leading to a higher xenon concentration due to the higher fission yield of ^{135}I of ^{239}Pu . Both these factors lead to decreased stability margin.

Fuel temperature feedback and moderator temperature feedback are important stabilizing phenomena and they are both closely connected to the heat conduction in the fuel rods. The fuel temperature feedback is basically instantaneous and is important for preventing small perturbations to grow due to xenon oscillations. The better the heat conduction, the more efficient the fuel temperature feedback will be. The moderator feedback is a weaker and slower effect that can be stabilizing or destabilizing depending on the phase lag compared to power changes. Heat conduction contributes to this phase lag

and if it is too poor, the moderator feedback will stabilize the reactor less efficiently or even act destabilizingly.

Xenon oscillations always occur in a thermal reactor. They become problematic when they are not inherently damped sufficiently. The problem of axial xenon oscillations can be divided into two different (but related) phenomena:

1. The physical reactor core is axially unstable
2. The calculational core model is axially unstable

When the physical reactor core is axially unstable, perturbations in control rod pattern, inlet temperature or reactor power may initiate a xenon oscillation which needs supervision and control. Depending on the degree of instability, the core may be difficult to control, and the thermal margins be reduced. That the physical reactor core is axially unstable usually implies that the calculational core model is axially unstable. The converse is not necessarily true. If the core model is axially less stable than the physical reactor core or behaves differently compared to the physical reactor core in terms of xenon transients, the reactor engineers may not be able to rely on the predictive calculations needed for core operation and surveillance. PWR axial stability has been previously studied in [2].

To estimate the susceptibility to axial xenon oscillations, for the physical reactor core or the core model, we define two parameters. The first parameter is the oscillation period, T . The second parameter is the damping ratio, defined according to equations (1) and (2) below. In equation (1) below, $AO(t)$ is the axial offset at time t , and n is an integer greater than, or equal to 1.

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{nT} \ln \frac{AO(t + nT)}{AO(t)} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} \zeta < 0: & \text{damped} \\ \zeta = 0: & \text{undamped} \\ \zeta > 0: & \text{divergent} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

To estimate the oscillation period and the damping ratio of the physical core, measured data of a free xenon oscillation is needed. For the core model, one can either simulate a real free xenon transient, or one can perturb the core model to initiate a fictitious xenon oscillation.

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE EVENT

On September 12, 2022, at 12:30 EEST, a free xenon oscillation was initiated in the Olkiluoto 3 reactor, as a part of the commissioning tests. The cycle exposure at the time of the start was around 72 EFPD. The oscillation was started by inserting the leading control rod group (P1) from initially 357 steps withdrawn to 307 steps withdrawn. The control rods were kept in this position throughout the test. The axial power distribution was measured both continuously using the fixed SPNDs and in discrete points using the aeroball measurement system (AMS). The process data: measured and calculated AO during the xenon oscillation are shown in Table 1 and Figure 2 below. Measured boron concentration is given in Table 1 both in terms of enriched boron concentration (Benr, 31.24 % ¹⁰B) and in terms of natural boron concentration (Bnat, 19.80 % ¹⁰B). Active coolant temperature (ACT) is given in °C.

Table 1. Process data during the xenon oscillation test.

Date	Time	Benr	Bnat	SPND	AMS	Power	ACT	P1
2022-09-11	21:05	520	831	-4.2	-3.8	78.7	311.8	357
2022-09-12	13:01	519	829	-7.1	-6.6	78.7	311.9	309
2022-09-12	13:40	519	829	-8.1	-7.2	78.6	312.0	307
2022-09-12	19:58	519	829	-10.3	-9.1	78.8	311.7	307
2022-09-13	00:53	519	829	-7.4	-6.5	79.4	311.8	307
2022-09-13	09:19	519	829	-3.2	-2.7	78.4	311.7	307
2022-09-13	17:16	520	831	-6.3	-5.5	78.4	311.8	307
2022-09-13	23:40	520	831	-8.1	-7.3	78.6	311.8	307
2022-09-14	06:05	517	826	-6.4	-5.7	78.4	311.7	307
2022-09-14	14:15	522	834	-4.4	-3.9	78.6	311.7	307

Figure 2. Measured and calculated AO during the xenon oscillation.

Excluding the bias at equilibrium conditions, the difference between measured (AMS) and calculated AO is less than 2.0 %. The calculated results are derived using Studsvik's state-of-the-art core monitoring system, CMS5 [3] and [4]. The base model uses the ENDF-BVII.I neutron cross-section evaluation.

4. SENSITIVITY TO NEUTRON DATA EVALUATIONS

In this chapter we investigate the impact of different neutron data evaluations on the axial stability of the core model, and specifically the agreement with measurement. The results for the oscillation period and the damping ratios are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Measured and calculated oscillation periods and damping ratios.

Model	Oscillation period (h)	Decay ratio (h ⁻¹)
E7R1	30.833	-0.006
E7R1 RUP	31.000	-0.009
E8R0	30.833	-0.006
E8R1	30.833	-0.006
JEF22	31.000	-0.007
JEF32	31.000	-0.006
JENDL4	30.666	-0.005
JENDL5	30.500	0.002
Measured (SPND)	30.200	-0.015

We see that for all models the calculated oscillation period is larger than the measured oscillation period. It is further seen that all calculational core models are less axially stable than the physical core. The core model based on JENDL5 is unstable and the core model based on ENDF-BVII.I with the advanced resonance upscattering model [1] activated agrees best with measurement in terms of the damping ratio. The core model based on JENDL5 gives the best agreement with measurement in terms of oscillation period. The comparison between measured and calculated AO is further shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Comparison between measured (SPND) AO and calculated AO for all models.

Table 3. Deviations between measured (SPND) and calculated AO

	E7R1	E7R1 RUP	E8R0	E8R1	JEF22	JEF32	JENDL4	JENDL5
RMS	0.896	0.619	0.930	0.903	0.844	0.896	0.981	2.036

It is clear from Figure 3 above that all models are very similar with respect to axial xenon oscillations. The two models that stand out are the model based on ENDF-BVII.I with the advanced resonance upscatter model activated, and the model based on the JENDL5-evaluation. It is also quite obvious that all core models oscillate more slowly than the physical core.

To investigate the cause of the poor behavior of the core model based on the JENDL5-evaluation, the cross-section data was replaced with the corresponding data from ENDF-BVII.I for ^1H , $^{155/157}\text{Gd}$, ^{235}U and ^{238}U . We have also included a model where the resonance overlap model in CASMO5 is activated for all nuclides. The results are shown below. Figure 4 shows the difference between the base JENDL5-model and the models with data replaced.

Figure 4. Difference in AO between the base JENDL5 model and the variations of it.

The impact of replacing the cross-section data in JENDL5 with data from ENDF-BVII.I has very small impact for the nuclides studied here. Replacing the cross-section data for ^1H and ^{235}U has a small impact, but all the other variations of the JENDL5-library give the same result as the base JENDL5-model. We can also see that replacing the data for ^1H and ^{235}U have cancelling effects. The model where ^1H cross-section data is replaced with cross-section data from ENDF-BVII.I is slightly more stable than the base JENDL5-model and all other variations show a similar behavior as the base JENDL5-model. Table 4 below shows the oscillation periods and the damping ratios for the base JENDL5-model and its variations.

Table 4. Measured and calculated oscillation periods and damping ratios for the JENDL5-models

Model	Oscillation period (h):	Decay ratio (h^{-1}):
JENDL5	30.500	0.002
JENDL5_H	30.500	0.001
JENDL5_GD	30.500	0.002
JENDL5_U235	30.333	0.002
JENDL5_U238	30.500	0.002
JENDL5_OVL	30.500	0.002
Measured (SPND)	30.200	-0.015

It is worth noting that the fission yield of ¹³⁵I, which is the main source of ¹³⁵Xe, is approximately 2.5% higher in the JENDL5-evaluation. The impact of the fission yield on axial stability will be investigated in future work.

5. SENSITIVITY TO HEAT CONDUCTION

Heat conduction in the fuel and the gas gap between the fuel pellet and the cladding are both very important for axial stability. Both parameters contribute to the phase lag between power changes and moderator temperature changes. The fuel heat conduction affects the speed and strength of the Doppler feedback.

In SIMULATE5, the gas heat conduction is modeled by two terms: the gaseous heat conduction, which controls the heat transfer from BOL until the gas gap closes, and the solid contact conduction, which controls the heat transfer from when the gas gap closes and onwards.

The fuel heat conduction is modeled in SIMULATE5 using a theoretical heat transfer coefficient multiplied by a burnup-dependent factor that describes the fuel fragmentation.

The sensitivity of the damping ratio and the oscillation period can be investigated by multiplying the gas heat transfer coefficient and fuel heat transfer coefficient by factors. This has been performed on the ENDFB-VII.I-model and the results are displayed as differences between measured and calculated damping ratios and oscillation periods in Figure 5 and 6 below.

htfue \ htgap	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,9	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,4	1,5
0,5	2,300	1,800	1,467	1,466	1,300	1,133	0,966	0,800	0,800	0,633	0,633
0,6	2,300	1,800	1,633	1,300	1,133	0,966	0,800	0,800	0,633	0,633	0,633
0,7	2,300	1,634	1,466	1,133	0,966	0,800	0,800	0,633	0,633	0,466	0,466
0,8	2,134	1,634	1,466	1,133	0,966	0,800	0,633	0,633	0,466	0,466	0,300
0,9	2,134	1,467	1,300	0,966	0,800	0,633	0,633	0,466	0,466	0,300	0,133
1,0	2,134	1,467	1,300	0,966	0,800	0,633	0,466	0,466	0,300	0,133	0,133
1,1	2,134	1,633	1,300	0,966	0,800	0,633	0,466	0,300	0,300	0,133	0,133
1,2	1,967	1,633	1,133	0,966	0,633	0,466	0,466	0,300	0,300	0,133	0,200
1,3	1,967	1,466	1,133	0,800	0,633	0,466	0,466	0,133	0,133	0,033	0,200
1,4	1,967	1,466	1,133	0,800	0,633	0,466	0,300	0,300	0,133	0,200	0,200
1,5	1,967	1,466	1,133	0,800	0,633	0,466	0,300	0,133	0,033	0,200	0,200

htfue \ htgap	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,9	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,4	1,5
0,5	0,004	0,002	0,001	0,000	0,002	0,003	0,004	0,005	0,006	0,007	0,008
0,6	0,004	0,002	0,000	0,001	0,003	0,004	0,006	0,007	0,008	0,010	0,010
0,7	0,004	0,002	0,000	0,002	0,004	0,006	0,007	0,009	0,010	0,011	0,013
0,8	0,003	0,002	0,000	0,003	0,005	0,007	0,009	0,010	0,012	0,013	0,015
0,9	0,003	0,001	0,001	0,003	0,006	0,008	0,010	0,012	0,014	0,015	0,017
1,0	0,003	0,001	0,001	0,004	0,007	0,009	0,011	0,013	0,015	0,017	0,019
1,1	0,003	0,001	0,002	0,005	0,007	0,010	0,012	0,015	0,017	0,019	0,020
1,2	0,003	0,000	0,002	0,005	0,008	0,011	0,013	0,016	0,018	0,020	0,022
1,3	0,003	0,000	0,003	0,006	0,009	0,012	0,014	0,017	0,019	0,022	0,023
1,4	0,003	0,000	0,003	0,006	0,010	0,013	0,015	0,018	0,020	0,023	0,024
1,5	0,003	0,000	0,003	0,007	0,010	0,013	0,016	0,019	0,022	0,024	0,025

Figure 5. Change in oscillation period (top, h) and damping ratio (bottom, h⁻¹)

The default heat transfer coefficients correspond to the adjustment factors being equal to 1.0, which are marked in bold face. It is clear from this sensitivity study that if the heat transfer coefficients are reduced to improve the damping ratio agreement, this will also worsen the agreement in oscillation period and

vice versa. The conclusion is that potential imperfections in the heat transfer model alone cannot explain the differences between measured and calculated damping ratio and oscillation period. Future physics model improvements and/or improvements in nuclear data evaluation may shift this apparent optimum.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have investigated the impact of different neutron data evaluations on the axial stability of the Olkiluoto 3 reactor. We have done so by comparing the measured and predicted axial offset during an intentionally started transient where the axial power distribution was allowed to oscillate freely for about 70 hours. Calculated results have been derived using Studsvik's state-of-the-art core monitoring system CMS5.

The analyses show that different neutron data evaluations give very similar results in terms of oscillation period and damping ratios. We have seen that the model based on ENDF-BVII.1 with the advanced upscatter model activated gives the best agreement to measurement. With this model, the difference between measured and calculated AO is below 1.0 % for almost the entire transient, which is a very good result. In the other end of the analysis, we see that the model based on the JENDL5-evaluation gives the poorest agreement with measurements.

When the cross-section data in JENDL5 was replaced by the corresponding data from ENDF-BVII.1, only a very small improvement is seen for ^1H , and an even smaller deterioration is seen for ^{235}U . The reason for the poor behavior of the JENDL5-model, in terms of axial xenon oscillations, is therefore still for the most part unknown. It is worth noting that the fission yield of ^{135}I , which is the main source of ^{135}Xe , is approximately 2.5% higher in the JENDL5-evaluation. The impact of the fission yield on axial stability will be investigated in future work.

The sensitivity study of varying heat conduction parameters for the fuel and the gap between cladding and pellet shows that potential shortcomings of the heat conduction model cannot alone explain the observed differences between measured and calculated damping ratio and oscillation period. This is because the parameters that gives the best agreement between measured and calculated damping ratio, give worse agreement between the measured and calculated oscillation period, and vice versa. Future physics model improvements and/or improvements in nuclear data evaluation may shift this apparent optimum.

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